

What the Recent Interventions in the Region has Taught us, is that, Free-Market Economy is a Fallacy, and What Really Matters is the Brutal Seizure of Resources and Mainly Energy Resources by World Powers

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Abstract

Any kind of energy production not harmonious with Earth's delicate and irreplaceable ecosystem constitutes harm to the fragile atmospheric and environmental stability of our planet. Furthermore, the disruption of the natural balance of our cradle might eventually threaten all life on Earth. Yet, most of the conventional energy production technologies fall into this category and supersede the harvesting of alternative energy resources more compatible with nature despite the devastating pollution they cause. Is the reason for this preference a purely financial one? We find this proposition not sincere at all. Whereas government-paid technocrats would have us believe that energy investments are the end result of painstakingly done technical studies based on years of meticulous research derived from immaculate scientific data, nothing could be further from the "truth". In a world where "might makes right", controlling energy is inevitably intertwined with casual politics, foul politics, and even, gory politics. The invasion – under the catchy title "Operation Iraqi Freedom" – of oilfields in Iraq by Coalition Forces in 2003, over the pretense that Saddam possessed weapons of mass destruction, can be seen as a thought-provoking validation of our statement. It is more suspect now than ever, that the world powers, although professing to uphold liberalism and democracy with zeal do not seem to care very much for "fair competition", much less, "fair trade", when dealing with cultures and civilizations alien to their own. To this end, they are known to stop at nothing to acquire what they aim for, through deception, subterfuge, and even – as was the case with their colonialist forefathers – callous violence. Consequently, it is understandable that these capitalistic conglomerations would not want to relinquish their hegemony over conventional energy sources to "inferior" Third World countries, and, as such, reap the long-term economical benefits from monopolizing these and obstructing substantial investments into renewable energy. Although, these parties appear to champion democracy and liberty, they, in fact, fully realize the importance of steering the masses via the presses and broadcasting networks in the battle for world energy supremacy. A brief analysis of the impact on the hindrance of the relatively fast development and deployment of unconventional energy resources, and mainly hydrogen energy, is undertaken in this contribution.

Keywords: Energy Resources, Energy wars, Free-Market Economy, Hydrogen Energy, Oil, World Powers.

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1. Introduction

At first glance, it may seem crude to pursue political issues on a highly technical level.

However, if these political issues concern how energy resources are regulated, then it is imperative that we adduce them here.

This we must do, even if it should mean exposing the Machiavellian ploys of world powers in their struggle to dominate global oil production.

Hence, the role played by imperious usurpers and masterminds who orchestrated the Iraq-Iran conflict, by 1980's and later, the invasion of Afghanistan and Iraq in 2003, in the so-called "preemptive warfare against global terrorism" to pave way for their multi-billion dollar oil monopolies will be the first topic of our analysis. [1]

Secondly, many of us are still inclined to believe that the global energy problem, and, by the same token, any local energy problem, can be scrutinized, managed, and resolved by just technical and scientific considerations.

According to such people, one can, by collecting data on the site, testing them in laboratories, and processing them in fancy computers, obtain supposedly optimized solutions to energy problems that should be lauded by all experts and cheered by the public.

While such parameters as *field data*, *laboratory results*, *mathematical modeling* and the calculation of the *optimization criteria* (which implies that the supply should be as *uncostly* and as *reliable* as possible) are no doubt indispensable inputs; the deciding factor on energy investment is ultimately the much overlooked *political opportunism*.

2. Development

2.1. One Vital Theorem

In this age, when engaging energy issues, there is one *vital theorem* that should be taken into consideration which can be summarized by the following statement. [2]

Theorem:

Wherever there is a widely used energy resource; casual politics, moreover, foul politics, and even, gory politics are at work.

This is certainly the case for oil. Following the depletion of world's oil resources, it would have been true for coal too, were it not for the fact that the greenhouse effect turned out to be as severe as it is actually perceived today. It would also be true for the still *finite* nuclear fuel in the world if only nuclear power production did not slump due to major accidents, public decial, and the problematic disposal of environmentally hazardous waste. It sure will be true in the case of water, if Earth's climate gets warmer and hydro resources become more and more scarce; in which event, water wars will likely take place.

2.2. The Free-Market Economy is a Sham, Organized Crimes Perpetrated by World Powers is All That Matters [2]

The author of this article, heartfully upholds freedom, democracy, alleviation of class differences and the institution of human rights. He is also a defender of "laissez faire" as long as it precludes the condoning of *labor exploitation* and *slavery* in the guise of liberty.

On the other hand, liberalist utterances by world powers can, in reality, mean anything in a global free-market economy but the actual essence of freedom, democracy, and human rights.

A fine example of this is the retaliation by capitalist great powers against the increase of oil prices in 1973 and 1979. [2, 3]

At that time, the "Organization of the Petroleum Exporting Countries" wanted to raise their oil prices, stating that, they did not possess any precious commodity other than oil, and that they were compelled to buy most goods from the Western

world anyway, and that Western manufacturers set the prices for their products as they willed according to the free-market rules of supply and demand, so, likewise, they too, should be entitled to determine oil prices as they chose. [2, 4, 5]

The Westerners, they suggested, [2, 6] might very well not buy as much oil at an increased price, if they found it expensive, and that, a decrease in the demand of oil might eventually induce a possible decrease in oil prices in the near future. After all, they said, this was the free-market where everyone traded fair and square.

This argument by oil exporting countries would have been very convincing if only the free-market economy as endorsed by the Western world was truly in effect.

Already in 1973, world powers were outraged by the decision of OPEC to raise their oil prices. As a reaction, they, in turn, gradually increased the prices for their export merchandise such as *automobiles, refrigerators, washing machines, and electronics*. [2]

This strategy counterbalanced the profits gained by OPEC, and continually reduced the revenues of oil lords. Therefore, OPEC decided to raise the oil prices once more in 1979.

It was a disaster for the Western world. The great powers were infuriated by the OPEC resolution to increase the purchase price of oil a second time, at which point, it was generally understood that a global free-market economy was advocated only as long as it profited the Western world.

In other words, it meant that *Westerners made all the business rules, and were entitled to fix the prices of commodities not only sold, but also, bought*. [2]

At this juncture, the author wishes to emphasize that he is not anti-Western; quite the contrary, he cherishes humanistic values and related institutions of the West.

He further admits that the phrases “*Westerners*” and “*Western world*” are poor denominations to stand for “*the plutocrats and decision-makers of the West*”, for he duly realizes that this faction constitutes only a scant minority, however influential, in the huge and complex intercontinental block encompassing North America, Europe and Australia. Nevertheless, for

lack of a better term, he shall, unjustly as it may be, consign to the usage of the above-mentioned phrases.

In any case, history shows that the Western world was extremely vexed by the increase in oil prices first in 1973, and then, in 1979, so much so that, when it came to maintaining their own side of the bargain in the *free-market economy*, they betrayed their hypocrisy. [2]

Shortly after, in 1980, Turkish Armed Forces were incited to carry out a *coup* in Turkey, and a little while later, Iraqi leader Saddam Hussein was instigated to assault Iran. [2, 7]

Sunni Arabs of Iraq and Shia Persians of Iran immediately found themselves in a bloody war. Striving for victory, each side attempted to sell more oil in return for arms and ammunition. By selling guns to both Iraq and Iran, Westerners recuperated their financial losses in petrodollars. Also, as enmity raged between the warring factions, oil prices fell. [2]

This is exactly why we say that the free-market economy is a sham, and what counts is mass-murders perpetrated through the Machiavellian machinations of villainous world powers.

That is not to say, however, that Iraq and Iran are not responsible for the bloodshed. They ought to share their due. But those who provoked these countries into a clash, and those same who sold them weapons throughout, are equally, if not more, accountable.

Saddam Hussein can indeed be classified as a *monster*, but he is a *miniature monster* compared to the miscreants who kindled this war between two peaceful neighbors, and continuously stoked them both with guns, carefully seeing to it that neither of them were, equipped with more weapons in order that the conflict might persist indefinitely.

While it was they who armed Saddam to the teeth, how is it that these crooks were moved into action only after two decades, in 2003, under the pretense that Iraq possessed weapons of mass destruction?

Historical events vindicate the above-mentioned theorem.

When practiced by capitalistic world powers, concepts such as “*freedom*”, “*democracy*”, “*human rights*” and “*liberal economy*”, despite any innate virtue they might possess, reduce to naught, but in fact a cover for their vile flagitiousness.

I believe, this is well demonstrated during the 2003 intervention of the Western world in Iraq. [8, 9]

It is horrifying to recall, when it was generally understood that Saddam killed 6800 Iraqis by toxic gas in Halabja (*i.e. well above twice the total of the World Trade Center victims, of 11 September, 2001*), the same Western world had set out to defend him by blaming Iran for the atrocities. [10]

2.3. What the World Powers Want

What do the world powers really want? The answer to this question is fairly simple: *“more power”*.

Power necessitates *“control”*. So, the basic motive is not actually a *need for energy*, but a *need for control*. While the global hunger for energy is always present, it would be disgraceful to consider it as the chief reason by which the aforesaid crimes against humanity have been committed.

On the other hand, the oil crises, in 1973 and in 1979 respectively, have taught the world how to use *energy efficiently* through unprecedented means and technologies. Finally, it became manifest to everyone that the world could sustain civilization by just *half* the energy it used to consume. [11]

At any rate, it would be

“much more effective, also more just, to ask educated individuals in developed nations to give up their sport utility vehicles and turn off the lights when they leave a room, than to demand that illiterate farmers in developing nations give up their natural needs and love for their children or to heinously bomb them”. [12, 13]

But, what the world powers want, is not simply *more energy*. They also yearn for *full control of energy resources*.

Since more than quarter a century, experts used to argue that the top priority in the Western world should be to *“Drain OPEC oil first”*. [14] It was a masterful stratagem never quite openly mentioned, and one which can be seen in operation even now.

If the world powers did not drain OPEC oil first, and were keen to invest in the harnessing of alternative

energy resources, they would perhaps not be in as much need of OPEC oil. But then, they would have abandoned a valuable asset to the hands of its native owners. Naturally, the capitalistic conglomerations would not consent to such a potential risk.

Therefore, OPEC oil reserves should at any rate flow, and be depleted permanently until the next phase.

This is the *essential cause* of why the lack of investment in alternative energy resources is not entirely *financial*.

It is true, that harnessing alternative energy resources is not as economical and as feasible compared to conventional resources. But pollution, which is not often included in our assessments, has a price too. The very dear price in fact. The discharge of carbon dioxide into the air due to the burning of coal and oil continually damages the ozone layer, allowing harmful rays to penetrate into Earth’s crust and do irreparable injury to living organisms.

Though every kind of energy investment has a price, life on earth is priceless.

So, the reason for which alternative energy resources are not yet explored thoroughly cannot simply be *financial*; it is, rather, the risk of leaving undrained oil resources out there as a power asset in the hands of their actual owners who might later become a threat that compels the world powers to prioritize the depletion of OPEC petroleum. [15, 16]

Similarly, *“democracy”* remains a virtue for world powers as long as they can manipulate the presses and broadcasting networks at their discretion to justify in the eyes of the public their monopolization of conventional energy production and forbearance toward renewable energy such as solar, wind and hydrogen, since, for the time being, they must maintain *firm political control* over the readily expendable oil.

The trends we summarized over here, as of now, endures with incomparable bloodshed in the Middle East, also in North of Africa, no doubt for oil, yet under efficient disguise, where you hear perpetually about democracy, human rights, and terrorism, but not anything about a drop of oil. This deserves further attention, which we will save though for a further work.

3. Conclusion

The reason for which conventional energy production was not so far replaced by alternative energy resources, and particularly, hydrogen energy despite the danger caused by the accumulation of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere, as well as various other advantages promised by renewable energy, cannot be *financial* alone.

The reason is not technological insufficiency either.

The reason is simply that the Western world wants to drain OPEC oil first, leaving not a single drop behind as an asset to its native owners no matter what the consequences of this severe strategy may be.

To this end, the world has witnessed once too often that the effrontery of great powers knows no bounds.

Eventually, humanity must either get rid of these wicked usurpers and opportunists who stop at nothing to attain ill-gotten gains, and endure until they deplete world's conventional energy resources to the last drop and ruin the planet by war and strife in the process, or unfortunately continue to suffer them after they have *monopolized* the means of alternative energy production, and still press on humanity, via holding in their hands, now, the novel means.

In conclusion, this happens to be their original *idea* of *democracy* and its *implementation*.

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